

AUTOMOTIVE GENERATOR DIAGNOSTIC MATRIX

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Abstract: In this article, a set of diagnostic parameters, features, technical condition and structure of the generator, and troubleshooting the basics of methods, diagnostic problems and ways to solve them are covered.

Key words: automobile, electrical and electronic equipment, structural and diagnostic parameters, generator diagnostic parameter, diagnostic matrix, diagnostic object.

Diagnostics of electrical and electronic equipment of cars and the application of its results in practice require speed and accuracy in today's transport. Diagnosing car units and preventing possible malfunctions requires a lot of knowledge. Using the diagnosis matrix, it helps to determine the interdependence of the malfunctions and their parameters, and to give a general conclusion on the elimination of breakdowns and malfunctions of the unit. It requires preliminary determination of the list of faults and the corresponding structural parameters, which can be eliminated using the diagnostic matrices (in fact, they are larger or larger); associated diagnostic parameters; relationships between the structural and diagnostic parameters indicated by the diagnostic matrix for the series or model of the diagnosed disorders are determined. In order to obtain diagnostic matrices, the real set of parameters of the internal technical state of the object, each of which can take an infinite set of values in a certain interval, is converted into a finite set of structural parameters $\{x\}$ that take only one of the two values 0 or 1. respectively to the absence or presence of a fault. Thus, the variable x_t conditionally reflects only the presence or absence of the i -th fault of the object I .

A set of diagnostic parameters, each of which can usually take an infinite set of values within a certain interval, as well as the standard values of diagnostic parameters S_m , which take one of two levels - 0 or 1, corresponding to the absence of malfunctions, or the presence of one or more faults.

Changing the indicators obtained during diagnostics according to diagnostic parameters consists in normalizing them:

- comparison of the indicator with the lower and upper standards that determine the tolerance area of the minimum t -th diagnostic parameter.
- the deviation of the t -th diagnostic parameter p_t from the distribution field is indicated by the value of the t -th diagnostic sign (symptom).

$$St. \begin{cases} p_t^l > p_t, \\ S_m = 1 \end{cases} \text{ and } \begin{cases} p_t^{ll} < p_t, \\ S_m = 1 \end{cases} \text{ or } \begin{cases} p_t^l < p_t < p_t^{ll}, \\ S_m = 0 \end{cases}$$

Here are the diagnostic parameter and its lower and upper limit values, respectively; St is a diagnostic feature.

Based on this theory, we will consider creating a structure-causal connection scheme and diagnostic matrix of the Lassetti car generator.

Function and structure of the diagnostic object

Figure 1. Lassetti car generator.

1 - generator output; 2 - body; 3 - back cover; 4 - connector; 5 - connecting screw; 6 - stator; 7 - front cover; 8 - Shkif

Below we mention the general elements of the generator.

Figure 2. Details and elements of the generator

1 - body; 2 – voltage regulator; 3 – electrical circuit; 4 - back cover; 5 - stator; 6 - rotor; 7 – fan; 8 - remote shutdown bushing; 9 – cover on the driving side; 10 - skiff; 11 - nut for fastening the pulley; 12 - rotor front bearings; 13 - protective washer of the rear bearing of the rotor from the winding side; 14- bearing on the back of the rotor; 15 - washer of the rear bearing of the rotor; 16 - connecting bolts; 17 - bolts for fixing the voltage regulator and rectifier block.

Based on the study of the structure of the generator and its reliability, a structural-causal scheme is drawn up. In this case, the following are determined:

- Diagnostic object: Generator;
- Structural elements of the generator: body; back cover; connector; connecting screw; stator; rotor, rotor bearing, front cover; Skiff
- Structural parameters of the elements: tension of the transmission belt and contact with the battery conditioner, loss of contact between the rotor of the generator brushes, burning of the stator coil, burning of the voltage regulator electrical circuit and violation of its adjustment.

Determining the characteristics of faults. The tension of the belt is measured and has an exact value for each brand of car. By means of ammeters and voltmeters, the insulation of the windings in the generator, the oxidation of the battery conditioner, the eating of the brushes are determined by visual inspection, and the burning of the

stator cores is detected by smell. A breakdown between the bearing and the rotor is determined by a change in noise.

Discharge of the battery while the car is running is manifested by power failure of electrical equipment, lack of power during ignition, and rapid power loss of the battery. Diagnostic signs for working and accompanying processes are determined in the following units: reduction of belt tension (N), maintenance of electric load, generator voltage 14V when the car is running, noise power -U, (W).

A diagnostic parameter is a physical unit that can be used to measure the working or companion processes of the object to be diagnosed. In our example, the tape tension is F, the power supply load is Q, or the noise power is U.

For the measurement of diagnostic parameters, TXK and JT processes and small-sized, uncomplicated, easy-to-use and high-precision measuring tools for automotive use are selected (MS008 - for the diagnosis of generators, starters and voltage regulators device).

. A diagnostic matrix is a two-valued logical model that shows the relationship between structural X and diagnostic S parameters that have reached a normative value.

Table 1

Diagnostic matrix of connection between structural and diagnostic parameters of the generator

Structural and diagnostic parameters		Structural parameters normative values		
		Generator belt tension	Generator drive belt tension	Tightness between the bearing and the rotor
Normative values of diagnostic parameters	Belt tension	1*	1	1
	The voltage generated in the generator	1	1	1
	Noise created by the rotation of the rotor and the rotor.	1	1	0*

Note: A number of "1" means that there is a possible fault, and a number of "0" means that there is no fault.

The diagnostic matrix does not indicate the probability or extent of faults, it only indicates the detection of faults based on a combination of diagnostic features. Relationships between structural parameters and diagnostic features are pre-established and included in the diagnostic matrix.

If it is known from observations of the operation of objects of the same type that there cannot be several failures at the same time (very unlikely), then all diagnostic parameters should be measured to determine it, "planned" by the matrix and as a result of the comparison, we can see that the combination of the diagnostic features with the matrix columns is related to the diagnostic parameters and the structural parameters and it is possible to determine their characteristics.

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CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND
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